

TOOL MATERIAL EFFECTS ON PROCESS INDUCED DEFORMATION OF COMPOSITE SPAR STRUCTURES

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1 Introduction

Process induced deformation in composite parts affects their qualities and demand a lot of efforts for the compensation. Many researchers have developed process modeling or simulation tools for predicting the deformation [1-3]. They are effective for cost and time saving in the development of composite parts. It is, however, difficult to establish the accurate modeling due to the complexity of the input parameters, such as material properties, boundary conditions of heat and mechanic, and tool - part interactions. Several methods for determining these input parameters were proposed by authors [4-6]. Also, process modeling to simulate tool-part interaction was proposed by Twigg, et al [7].

Recently, carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) tools have become more popular thanks to improvement of tough resin systems in high temperature condition. CFRP tools are considered to be beneficial due to lighter weight, lower heat capacity, and matching coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) with a part. However, CFRP tool material effects on process induced deformation have not known well.

In this work, tool material effects on process induced deformation of composite wing spar structures were investigated using three tools made of different materials: aluminum, invar and CFRP.

2 Experiments

2.1 Preparation of Specimens

A wing spar is typically shaped like a C channel and this kind of part exhibits three types of process induced deformations, which are flange spring-in, web warpage away from the tool, and corner thinning [8]. Also, web height change from the design is important for wing assembly. These deformations are schematically described in Fig. 1.

For the sake of ease in understanding these phenomena, simple shaped specimens were made in this work. Six specimens with two thicknesses, which were quasi isotropic 8-ply and 16-ply, made on the three tools were prepared. The specimen configurations are shown in Table 1. All specimens designed a same mold line and a uniform cross section. The web height is 600 mm, the both side flange length and angle are 100 mm and 90 degree respectively, the corner radius is 8 mm and the width of specimen is 120 mm.

Three convex (male) tools were used for curing the specimens. The each tool was made of different materials which were aluminum, invar and CFRP. Surfaces of the aluminum tool and the invar tool were machined and finished by sanding. Woven fabric epoxy resin prepregs were used for the CFRP tool and the CFRP tool shown in Fig.2 was made by means of curing on a concaved master tool.

Before laying up the specimen's prepregs, release agent, Frekote®700-NC, was applied on the surfaces of the tools. After laying up and bagging, three specimens on the different material tools were cured simultaneously in an autoclave. Three 8-ply specimens were manufactured first, then the three 16-ply specimens were manufactured using the same tools. The process of specimen manufacturing is shown in Fig.3.

2.2 Non-contact Full Field Measurement

In this work, full field measurements using a high resolution non-contact structured light 3D scanner, ATOS-II (GOM), were conducted to measure the detail shape of the specimens and the tools.

Angle measurements of the tool surface by a clinometer, CLINOTRONIC PLUS®, were conducted before the 3D scanner measurements and the angle data were compared to confirm the accuracy of the 3D scanner. Figure 4 shows the

location of the angle measurements and the measurement situation. Table 2 shows the results of the measurement. The tool surface angles were almost same as the designed shape within ± 0.11 degree.

The specimens reclined on one side for minimizing a gravity effect during the 3D scanner measurement as shown in Fig. 5, while the tools stood on the flange edges. Inner and outer surfaces of the specimens and an outer surface of the tools were digitized and the center cross section data were used to calculate the shape parameter described in Fig.1.

An example of the digitized surface at the cross section of the tool is presented in Fig.6. The web is almost horizontal and flat, and the flanges are almost vertical.

The shape parameters of the tools are summarized in Table 3. The web height errors were within ± 0.15 mm to the design. All the flange angles were almost vertical and identical within the difference of 0.03 degree to measured angles by the clinometer as shown in the location A and E columns of Table 2. The webs of the aluminum tool and invar tool were almost horizontal and flat. The CFRP tool, however, sagged in the middle of the web slightly and the angle measurement by the clinometer had the same trend as shown in the CFRP row of the location B and D columns of Table 2.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Deformation of specimens

As an example of the digitized surface at the cross section of the specimen, the measurement result of the CF-8 is presented in Fig.7. Unlike in the case of the tools, web warpage and flange spring-in can be observed obviously. Summary of the shape parameters of the specimens is shown in Table 4. Web height changes, web warpings and flange spring-in angles were calculated by subtracting the values of the tools from ones of the specimens and are shown in Fig.8.

As expected, the specimens cured on the aluminum tool had the largest and positive web height changes due to CTE mismatch between the aluminum tool and the CFRP specimens. And the invar tool and the CFRP tool could make the specimens with a little negative web height change, and the specimen cured on the CFRP tool was the smallest error from the

tool due to matching the CTEs between the tool and the specimen.

The measurement results showed that spring-in and web warpage depended on the thickness of the specimens. Thinner specimens had larger spring-in angles and web warpings.

Web warpings of the specimens cured on the CFRP tool were larger than ones cured on the aluminum tool and the invar tools. The warpage depends on the tool-part interfacial shear stress developing during processing and the stress goes higher in the sticky condition at a tool-part interface [7]. Although same treatment before processing on all tool surfaces was conducted, the CFRP tool surface was considered to be sticky more than the aluminum and invar tool surfaces.

Spring-in angles of the specimens cured on the aluminum tool and the invar tool were almost same, even though the CTEs of the tools are extremely-different. Spring-in angles of the parts made on the CFRP tool were smaller than others. Spring-out of the CFRP tool during processing is considered as the reason.

Comparing to the spring-in angles of L-shaped specimens shown in Table 5 [9, 10], the spring-in angles in this work were much larger, especially for the 8-ply specimens. The specimens in this experiment had large web warpings and the definition of the flange spring-in angle in this work is the deflection from the vertical line to the designed web line. Web angle rotations caused by web warpage need to be calculated to evaluate the flange spring-in correctly.

Deflections at the corner exit and 50 mm from the corner exit on the inner surface of the specimens were used to calculate the web rotations.

Figure 9 shows the spring-in angles separated into the spring-in component and the web warpage component. For the specimens cured on the aluminum tool and the invar tool, the spring-in angles without the web rotation component are almost same as the spring-in angles of the L-shaped specimens, such as about 1.3 degree at 8-ply specimens and about 1.2 degree at 16-ply specimens. As mentioned in section 3.1, the specimens cured on the CFRP tool have small spring-in component due to the spring-out of the CFRP tool. The presumption of 0.8 degree in the spring-out of the CFRP tool could make the same spring-in angles to the specimens cured on the other tools.

3.2 Thickness variation

An example of thickness distribution of the specimens is presented in Fig.10. Thinner at the corner regions and thicker at the corner exit regions could be observed. All the thicknesses at the center cross section of the specimens are shown in Fig.11. The specimens cured on the aluminum tool had larger decrease in the thickness at the corner regions than others. Figure 12 shows the minimum thicknesses change at the corner and the maximum thicknesses change at the corner exit relative to the average thicknesses of the whole cross section. While the corner thinning of the specimens cured on the aluminum tool had much larger than ones cured on the invar tool and the CFRP tool, the thickening at the corner exit had less differences among all specimens within 0.1 mm to 0.2 mm.

3.3 Numerical process modeling

In this section, the experimental problem is analyzed by comparison to the numerical predictions, including the tool-part interactions determined from the experiments. Using the FE package MSC Marc version 2010, full 3D models of the parts, 8-ply and 16-ply were created. 20-node composite brick elements setting two elements in through the thickness direction were used for taking account of the laminate constitution, and the tool was not modeled, see Fig. 13. Material properties used in this model were obtained by author, et.al. [4, 9].

In order to implement tool-part interactions, thin shear layer element were proposed [11]. Practically, however, determination of the adequate properties of this element is difficult due to complex phenomena in process, such as sliding, sticking and effects by tool surface condition or resin cure status. For sake of ease, constant shear forces were applied on the inner surface of the parts in this work as shown in Fig. 14. The shear forces were set to be coincident with the experimental data of web warpage.

The results of the numerical predictions are shown in Fig. 15. Comparing to the experimental data shown in Fig.9, web warpage components were smaller on all specimens, but spring-in components were a little larger, and total spring-in angles were almost same.

Theoretical approach to determination of the tool-part interaction effects is the next step.

4 Conclusions

In this study, detailed shape profiles of C-shaped parts were investigated for different tool materials using the 3D scanner.

As expected, CTE of tool material affected the web height change of the parts, and the CFRP tool was the most suitable for obtaining an accurate web height.

Web warpages and spring-in angles did not depend on the tool CTE unexpectedly. The specimen cured on the CFRP tool had larger web warpages than the ones cured on the metal tools. In the case of C-shaped parts, spring-in angles were subjected to the influence of the web warpages.

Thickness distributions were also investigated, and thinner corner was obtained in the specimen cured on the aluminum tool.

Numerical process modeling was conducted including the tool-part interaction. The FE results were in good agreement with the experimental results, but need to be theoretical background of the tool-part interaction.

Fig.1. Schematic of typical process induced deformations of C channel made on a convex tool.

Table 1 Configuration of the specimens

Specimen ID	Tool material	Lay up
AL-8	Aluminum	[45/0/-45/90] _s
AL-16	Aluminum	[45/0/-45/90] _{2s}
IN-8	Invar	[45/0/-45/90] _s
IN-16	Invar	[45/0/-45/90] _{2s}
CF-8	CFRP	[45/0/-45/90] _s
CF-16	CFRP	[45/0/-45/90] _{2s}

Fig.2. CFRP tool for experiments.

(a) Location of tool angle measurement and definition of the angle

(a) Specimen lay up on the aluminum tool

(b) Photograph of the tool angle measurement

Fig.4. Tool angle measurement by a clinometer

Table 2 Results of tool angle measurement by the clinometer

Tool	Location				
	A	B	C	D	E
Aluminum	0.02	0.01	0.00	-0.02	-0.06
Invar	0.08	0.03	0.00	-0.04	-0.10
CFRP	0.05	-0.08	0.00	0.10	-0.11

Unit : degree

All angles were compensated by the measurement angles of the location C

(b) Autoclave setting

(c) Specimen after curing

Fig.3. Specimen manufacturing

Fig.5. Photograph of the shape measurement of a specimen by the 3D scanner.

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(a) Whole shape

(b) Enlarged display at curved region of the left side
Fig.6. Digitalized cross section shape of the CFRP tool

(a) Whole shape

(b) Enlarged display at curved region of the left side
Fig.7. Digitalized cross section shape of the specimen, CF-8

Table 3 Summary of the tool shape measurement by the 3D scanner

Tool material	Web height [mm]	Web warpage [mm]	Flange angle [degree]	
			Left side	Right side
Aluminum	599.85	0.04	0.04	-0.05
Invar	599.94	0.06	0.07	-0.10
CFRP	600.11	-0.35	0.08	-0.13

Table 4 Summary of the shape measurement of the specimens by the 3D scanner

Specimen ID	Web height [mm]	Web warpage [mm]	Flange angle [degree]	
			Left side	Right side
AL-8	601.60	1.92	2.02	-2.15
AL-16	601.69	0.90	1.58	-1.61
IN-8	599.51	1.59	2.14	-2.04
IN-16	599.56	0.70	1.62	-1.65
CF-8	599.72	2.68	1.71	-1.80
CF-16	599.97	0.82	0.90	-0.99

(a) Web height change

(b) Web warpage

(c) Flange spring-in angle

Fig.8 Results of deformation measurements

Table 5 Spring-in angles of L-shaped specimens with quasi-isotropic constitution [9, 10]

Tool material	The number of ply	Spring-in angle [degree]
Aluminum	8	1.22
		1.49
	16	1.19
		1.13
Invar	8	1.23
		1.32
		1.33

Fig.9. Spring-in angles separated into the spring-in component and the web rotation component

Fig.10. Thickness distribution of the specimen, AL-16 measured by the 3D scanner

(a) Aluminum tool

(b) Invar tool

(c) CFRP tool

Fig.11. Thicknesses of the specimens at the center cross section

(a) Minimum thickness at corner

(b) Maximum thickness at the corner exit

Fig.12. Thickness changes at the corner and the corner exit relative to the average thickness

(a) Whole model

(b) Enlarged display at curved region

Fig.13. FE model of the C-shaped specimen

Fig.14. Schematic cross section for showing shear forces applied on the part inner mold line of FE model

Fig.15. FE results of spring-in angles separated into the spring-in component and the web rotation component (Spring-in components of the CF-8 and CF-16 decreased by 0.8 degree for compensation of the CFRP tool's spring-out)

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